

Scottish Land Use Policy Coherence – Joining Up across Domains

The Scottish Government seek an agricultural and land use **transformation** to tackle the climate and biodiversity crises and maintain viable rural economies in a just and inclusive way. **Policy Coherence** can help to ensure different policy **objectives** are consistent, the different policy **instruments** are coordinated, and there is strong **collaboration** within Government.

Figure shows coherence between the different policy domains. The squares represent primary legislation and circles represent steering strategies. Coloured arrows show references between the referencing policies and the policies that are referenced. There are 169 connections between policies in all four policy domains but only 13 **reciprocal relationships**. It is unclear if the connections are always **understood and considered in design or delivery**, particularly where the link is only one-way.

Scottish Land Use Policy Coherence – Joined Up Government

Figure shows how several policies - often steering strategies (circles) - are connected to multiple policy directorates (hexagons).

This supports our starting contention that land use is a broad and cross governmental policy issue. **However, it is not clear if these links are active collaborations.**

Some 'missing' connections may exist in practice, but without being stated, could be invisible to those from other parts of government who wish to practice coherence. **Explicit explanations of policy connections and their implications in policy documents** could help the practice of coherence.

54 policy documents

- primary legislation (18) Squares
- strategies (36) circles

16 Agricultural policies

5 Climate policies

17 Environment policies

16 Socio-economic policies

Associated with Agriculture and Rural Economy Directorate (14); - Environment and Forestry Directorate (13); - Energy and Climate Change Directorate (12) and 17 other directorates and agencies

Further information can be found in a [briefing](#) and [report](#)

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